

REPORT A CASE STUDY IN APACHE OPENOFFICE SOFTWARE

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Abstract.

Apache Open Office (AOO) is not just a program; it is also an open-source project that anyone can use for free. Open-source software can be used instead of expensive software for changing documents. Apache Open Office has the same features as popular, expensive software packages. This free, open-source software tool can make papers in Word, Excel, PowerPoint, and PDF forms, among others. Apache Open Office is a free option to expensive tools for changing documents that students, teachers, and businesses can use to save money and make documents that are just as good.

1 Introduction

1.1. Apache OpenOffice (AOO) is a free and open-source office productivity suite. OpenOffice.org and IBM Lotus Symphony both see it as their eventual replacement. Similar to NeoOffice, Collabora Online, and LibreOffice in 2014. It has a text editor (called Writer), a spreadsheet (called Calc), a presentation app (called Impress), a drawing app (called Draw), a formula editor (called Math), and a database manager (called Base).

1.2. OpenOffice is a free and open-source software suite that may be used as a substitute for Microsoft Office. Like Microsoft Office, it has a word processor, spreadsheet, and presentation maker that are all very user-friendly and capable of producing professional-quality documents. OpenOffice has been making inroads into the home and office environments in recent years. Due to improved compatibility with Microsoft file formats and steadily decreasing company and personal budgets, OpenOffice has become a popular alternative office suite for

those searching for a cost-effective solution. Since 2005, when they made the move to OpenOffice, the French police had saved over €2 million.

2. Why I should choose Apache OpenOffice

As to Why Apache OpenOffice

When it comes to free, open-source alternatives for common office tasks like document editing, Excel, PowerPoint, graphics, and database management, Apache OpenOffice is unrivaled. It is compatible with any standard PC and comes in several languages. All of your information is saved in an industry-standard open format, and it is compatible with the majority of office suites. It is available for no cost to download and use in any way you see fit.

Superb program

Over twenty years of dedicated software development went into creating Apache OpenOffice. Its constancy is unparalleled by competing items because it was developed as a whole. Anyone may submit fixes, feature requests, or code improvements in a fully open development process. As a consequence, Apache OpenOffice is fully functional office software that meets all of your needs.

Functionally simple

If you are familiar with another office suite, you will have no trouble picking up Apache OpenOffice. Because of our massive international user base, OpenOffice is likely to be translated and is available in your local tongue. OpenOffice can also read files created in other office suites with little to no trouble.

Free of charge

The best part is that there are no costs associated with downloading or using Apache OpenOffice. Apache OpenOffice is open source and available at no cost thanks to the Apache Software Foundation. As with version 2.0, Apache OpenOffice may be downloaded and used freely. That makes it fair game for personal, professional, academic, and government use. Any number of PCs can have it installed. You are free to photocopy and distribute as many copies as you would like to anybody you would like

History and Evolution of Apache OpenOffice

The Apache Software Foundation: What Is It?

The Foundation for Apache Software (ASF) is a United States-based 501(c) 3 nonprofit corporation whose primary goals are to:

Provide hardware, communication, and infrastructure for businesses for open, collaborative projects to develop software and establish a separate legal entity to which businesses and individuals can donate with confidence that their money, will be used for the public good.

Provide protection for volunteers against lawsuits aimed at the Foundation's activities.

Safeguard the use of the "Apache" name with reference to its software from unauthorized parties. That is the cold, hard reality, but how did this come to be, what does it all mean, exactly? We have to go back in time just a bit.

3.1 Some background

In 1999 a collective of individuals calling themselves the "Apache Group" established the foundation with the intention of maintaining the NCSA's HTTPD web server.

However, the original creators of that server eventually lost interest in it and went on to other projects, leaving users without any support despite the fact that the server was freely accessible, came with source code, and had been granted under a license that permitted highly open modification and redistribution.

Some of these end users then began trading fixes (patches) and knowledge on how to avoid issues and enhance the product. Brian Behlendorf established an email list on his personal computer so that users may work together on updates and enhancements to the program.

The Apache moniker has been selected out of awe and admiration for the legendary warrior abilities and unyielding fortitude of the Native American Indian tribe of that name. The term ("patchy web server") refers to a server that has been built together from various components, and the term itself is a funny play on that idea. The team of programmers responsible for this groundbreaking release eventually came to refer to itself as "The Apache Group." The Apache Group's Apache HTTPD Web Server developed between 1995 and 1999, quickly became the industry standard (and continues to be so, powering more than 65% of all websites).

However, as the web expanded and commercial interests arose, additional sister projects (like the mod_perl project, the PHP project, and the Java Apache project) were housed on the Apache website. There was a growing awareness of the necessity for a more unified and well-structured organization to protect individuals against possible legal threats.

3.2 About Mikeal Rogers

About twelve years ago, at a period when both corporations and members of the open-source movement were wary of one another, Apache was established. Not much has changed: large corporations continue to exploit open source certification as an instrument of advertising (a practice known as "open washing"), and some in the industry are still skeptical about open source, especially when related to certain types of licenses.

There is probably no large company in existence today that does not use open-source software in some form. Moreover, it is difficult to think of a contemporary technology company that does not employ open-source software in some way. You must rely on open-source software for at least a portion of your stack since no corporation has the capacity to license or create all the necessary technological advances for launching a new product.

Companies may no more have the same prejudices against open-source software, but developers' need for privacy guarantees keeps the Apache mission current. As time has gone, the patent issues which have troubled people for decades have become even more pervasive. Stronger legal protections for intellectual property are more important than ever for open-source software creators.

One thing that has kept Apache consistent throughout the years is its belief that "Via a cooperative and a merit-based process of development [Apache delivers] software goods that attracted a significant number of users." This perspective was originally created and utilized in a quite different setting. Why do numerous individuals appear attracted to this approach, and what exactly is it?

Open-source projects had far more hurdles to jump over ten years ago. It was a huge headache to host the source code. Hosting a wiki, a mailing list, and a bug tracker – services we today take for granted – were not trivial to set up and manage even five years ago. Theoretical problems also arose. What prevented one corporation from eventually taking control of a large-scale project? How did one business prevent a rival firm from gaining control of a project? Because of these and other concerns, a set of procedures and rules was established to regulate things like project votes and committee elections, and privileges.

4. Connecting to an Address Book in OpenOffice.org

Introduction

This document's stated goal is to provide a description of the technologies involved in bringing the address-book feature to OpenOffice.org and Mozilla, including an overview of the address-book types offered and the corresponding underlying APIs and an architecture diagram illustrating the common and distinct components included in both suites. OpenOffice.org has a handy appendix detailing the Mozilla files it automatically installs, down to the platform specifics.

4.1 Background

Based on the design of Java's JDBC, OpenOffice.org has open access to databases API named SDBC (Sun DataBaseConnectivity). SDBC has a flexible provider design that allows it to handle a number of databases and database-like

APIs. These include ODBC 3.0, JDBC, ADO, dBase, and CSV. The OpenOffice.org component technology, UNO, is used to build each SDBC provider.

Email clients like Mozilla's Messenger and Microsoft's Outlook both include their own internal address book (contacts) databases and can sync with a centralized directory service like LDAP. The XPCOM technology that powers Mozilla extensions is a portable ("XP") components (object model) system.

4.2 Glossary

Mozilla is the Netscape browser's open-source project and release.

AbZilla is a project for Mozilla that is a contact book.

XPCOM stands for "cross-platform component object model" and is Mozilla's in-process component middleware technology.

UNO is the open cross-platform component object model for OpenOffice.org.

SDBC is Sun DataBaseConnectivity

JDBC - Java's flexible database API

Outlook is the fully licensed form of the Microsoft Outlook Express email app. It has features like group calendaring and peer-to-peer sharing.

Outlook Express is a mail client that is a cut-down version of Microsoft Outlook. It comes with Microsoft Internet Explorer and replaces the MS Mail client.

WAB files are from the MS Windows AddressBook (.wab).

PAB stands for MS Exchange® PersonalAddressBook.

CSV stands for "Comma-SeparatedValues," which is an exchange format for tables or other groups of property values that are repeated.

COM stands for Common Object Model, which is Microsoft's technology for simple object components.

MAPI is a standard C API for full-function messaging, calendaring, and contact books.

4.3 Supported Address Books

Multiple address book formats are supported. Every data source can be reached through an XPCOM supplier component, which utilizes a specific address-book API, as shown in the table below. The address books displayed in bold are accessible for all Mozilla platforms as well whereas the others can only be used on Windows.

Mail Client	Address Book Type	API
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Any	LDAP	Mozilla's LDAP XPCOM component
Mozilla	Local address book	Mozilla address-book XPCOM component
Outlook	Outlook Personal Address Book (PAB)	MAPI
Outlook Express / MS Mail	Windows Address Book (WAB)	WAB API

ARCHITECTURE AS WAS MENTIONED ABOVE, IT WAS DECIDED TO USE A UNIFIED SET OF COMPONENTS TO MAKE MOZILLA'S EMAIL CLIENT AND OPENOFFICE.ORG SDBC'S ADDRESS BOOK ACCESSIBLE VIA THE INTERNET. SINCE XPCOM IS USED TO INCORPORATE NEW FEATURES INTO MOZILLA, AN ADAPTER FOR MICROSOFT OUTLOOK AND OUTLOOK EXPRESS'S ADDRESS BOOKS WAS BUILT AND EXPOSED THROUGH AN XPCOM API. AN LDAP ADDRESS BOOK WAS ALSO SUPPORTED BY USING AN ALREADY EXISTING XPCOM LDAP ELEMENT.

WIDELY USED IS THE OPENOFFICE.ORG COMPONENT TECHNOLOGY KNOWN AS THE UNO OBJECT. THE SDBC DESIGN SUPPORTS ADAPTOR UNO COMPONENTS FOR EACH ADDITIONAL DATA SOURCE, MUCH LIKE THE XPCOM COMPONENTS USED BY MOZILLA'S ADDRESS-BOOK PROVIDER ARCHITECTURE. A UNO COMPONENT THAT EXPOSES AN ADDRESS BOOK DATA SOURCE IS REQUIRED FOR INTEGRATING THE ABZILLA ADDRESS BOOK ELEMENTS INTO OPENOFFICE.ORG.

TO ENSURE MOZILLA COMPATIBILITY, XPCOM WAS MOSTLY USED TO SET UP THE ADDRESS-BOOK PROVIDERS IN THE SELECTED ARCHITECTURE. TO MAKE THESE XPCOM INTERFACES ACCESSIBLE TO OPENOFFICE.ORG, A UNO INTERFACE ADAPTER WRAPS THEM IN A PROPRIETARY C++ API. THE FOLLOWING FIGURE SUMS UP THIS ARCHITECTURE:

(Figure 1: OpenOffice.org and Mozilla have the same address book design.)

To integrate the address book features of Mozilla with OpenOffice.org's SDBC architecture, the project provides two libraries:

libmozab2.so, which employs libmozabdrv2's (secret) C++ API to construct a UNO-based SDBC provider.so

libmozabdrv2.so, which leverages its AbZila address-book XPCOM-based elements (and hence XPCOM and its dependencies) and provides a (private) C++ API.

Use of the XPCOM APIs exposed by the PAB, WAB Moz-AB, and Moz-LDAP address-book providers requires the XPCOM core architecture and associated dependencies.

OpenOffice.org currently includes 50 Mozilla files in total, including the following for compatibility with the AbZilla XPCOM-based address-book components:

- = the fundamental libraries for XPCOM technology from Mozilla
- = file configurations
- = JavaScript and several more dependent libraries are required to access XPCOM's configuration.
- = The library includes the four unique XPCOM components for address books (PAB, WAB, Mozilla AB, and Mozilla LDAP).

Because certain necessary bug fixes created by the project team have not yet been accepted into the usual Mozilla build, the Mozilla libraries included with OpenOffice.org are not totally built from the typical Mozilla CVS trunk. A

summary bug report with a list of these fixes may be found at http://www.openoffice.org/issues/show_bug.cgi?id=8239. As Mozilla is not fully bundled and cannot be assumed to be pre-installed, the Mozilla dependencies are distributed with (and installed by) OpenOffice.org. If these fixes were integrated into Mozilla, OpenOffice.org could use the dependent files from a standard Mozilla installation by pointing a Mozilla environment variable at the Mozilla distribution.

5. Why Apache OpenOffice: Non-Profit Organization

Large and small NFPs alike are using Apache OpenOffice because it is flexible, secure, and aligned with their missions. The office suite's many features, including a dynamic graphics editor, database access, and an adaptable word processor, exceed expectations.

OpenOffice is very compatible with a commercial computer program, but it does not come with the associated price tag or licensing hassles.

1. All-inclusive software

Non-profits, more than ever, must be able to stand out in a crowded field. Non-profits may now afford the same high-quality office software that large corporations use, thanks to Apache OpenOffice. OpenOffice is a well-tested, reliable program that has been refined over twenty years. OpenOffice is a driving force in the global push to ensure that everyone, regardless of their financial situation, has access to high-quality computing tools. Participate in OpenOffice's global community to make new connections, get insight, or get answers to any questions you may have.

2. Superior, but compatible

Apache OpenOffice is proud of its ability to work with various office suites. Non-profits that depend on volunteers will be pleased to learn that OpenOffice is intuitive even for those who have never used it before. Because no company is an island, OpenOffice may share documents with different office suites. It also supports the creation of PDF files, which come in handy if you need to keep some kind of control over a document even after it has left your workplace. The program is the first of its kind to provide such a secure long-term home for your most valuable data under an internationally recognized standard.

3. All doors open

Amazingly, Apache OpenOffice has no hidden costs or licensing agreements. You are free to put it for any reason, distribute copies to your staff, fans, etc., and download it onto as many devices as you wish. OpenOffice supports many different languages and constantly recruits local teams to translate even more. OpenOffice is the simplest and most cost-effective approach to provide non-profits

(including charities, voluntary sector groups, etc.) the core software applications they need to function efficiently.

6. Complicated programs are written by unpaid individuals?

Volunteers make up the whole development team for Apache Open Office. Developers, translators, QA, marketing, UI, support, and so forth are not compensated in any way by Apache. Donations to the Apache Software Foundation are gratefully accepted and used to cover operational costs like maintaining their servers. However, all of their items are created by unpaid individuals.

This may cause immediate alarm among certain users. But how reliable can free software be if it's made entirely by unpaid volunteers?

6.1 Staff members on the same level as any major company

Many experts have contributed to OpenOffice over the past decade and a half, and many continue to do so today. A number of the volunteers have been sent there by their companies. Sun, Oracle, Novell, Red Hat, IBM, and a number of other companies have funded workers' participation in OpenOffice development at various points in time. Some of the contributors are recent retirees who want to maintain their skills current or who want to "give back" to the open-sourced community by contributing to the project. Some contributors run a consultancy firm based on OpenOffice and use their time on the project as a way to network with other professionals and possible clients. There are also students involved who are learning the ropes of software development through an online internship. Several OpenOffice contributors have been working on OpenOffice for more than ten years, and they are all volunteers. Numerous companies are unwilling to have as much talent as OpenOffice has employed on this.

Thus, as a non-profit organization, its all-volunteer principle describes its structure. No developer is ever paid by OpenOffice. This, however, is not a reflection on the skill or dedication of their unpaid staff. In reality, only a few companies could afford the caliber of skill they have on the Apache OpenOffice team thanks to their volunteer efforts.

7. Some Products of Apache OpenOffice

1. Apache OpenOffice Math

Simple to write equations and formulas for your documents using Apache OpenOffice Math

$$f(x, y) = \frac{e^M \cdot \sqrt{\cos(x) + \tan(y)}}{M^2}$$

Equations may be found in Apache OpenOffice's Math component. It may be used with various document kinds or independently, although it is most often used as an equation editor for text documents. The equation is handled as an object in the text document when used within Writer. Similarly to that, they may also be added to Calc and Impress in Apache OpenOffice.

There are three primary methods for inserting a formula in Math:

- In the equation editor, type markup.
- To choose a symbol from the context menu, right-click the equation editor and choose it.
- From the Elements toolbox, choose a symbol.

2. Apache OpenOffice Impress

With your presentations, wow your audience!

Impress is an incredibly good tool for making successful multimedia presentations. With 2D and 3D clip art, special effects, animation, and powerful sketching tools, your presentations will stand out.

Creating your content is made easier using Master Pages. By obtaining templates from our

Templates collection, you may save even more time.

A full variety of Views are available, including an optional multi-pane view that puts all the resources at your fingertips. These Views include Slides, Outlines, Notes, and Handouts to fulfill the demands of presenters and audiences.

While presenting their slides on a projector, presenters might have access to supplementary information or note thanks to several displays. Make the most of this by using the integrated Presenter Screen, which allows you to check the time, speaker notes, and your next slides.

3. Apache OpenOffice Calc

The answer to keeping track of all your numbers and lists!

The spreadsheet program you've been looking for is Calc. Beginners find it straightforward and simple to understand, while experts in data mining and figure crunching will value the wide variety of sophisticated functionalities.

With the use of cutting-edge technology called DataPilot, it is simple to extract raw data from business databases, cross-tabulate it, compile it, and turn it into useful information.

You may build formulae using natural language (for instance, "sales - costs") formulas.

Depending on the situation, the Intelligent Sum Button automatically adds a subtotal or a sum function.

Wizards walks you through selecting and utilizing a wide variety of complex spreadsheet functions, or you may download pre-made spreadsheet solutions from our Templates library.

Applying versatile cell formatting choices, such as freely rotating content, templates, backdrops, borders, and many more, is simple using Styles & Formatting. Thanks to templates with built-in functionality, you can become your own spreadsheet expert and focus on your actual job.

With the push of a button, Scenario Manager enables "what if" analysis, such as comparing profitability for high, medium, and low sales projections.

8. Installation Process of Apache OpenOffice

Free alternative for Office productivity tools: Apache OpenOffice - formerly known as OpenOffice.org - is an open-source office productivity software suite containing a word processor, spreadsheet, presentation, graphics, formula editor, and database management applications. OpenOffice is available in many languages, works on all common computers, stores data in ODF - the international open standard format - and is able to read and write files in other formats, including the format used by the most common office suite packages. OpenOffice is also able to export files in PDF format. OpenOffice has supported extensions, in a similar manner to Mozilla Firefox, making it easy to add new functionality to an existing OpenOffice installation.

8.1 How can I get OpenOffice set up on a Windows computer and other Operating Systems?

1. Installing OpenOffice.org on Windows Computers

The installation file for Windows from [OpenOffice download](#) is a self-extracting EXE file. Download the file. Your browser will save the file to your hard drive.

- Locate the downloaded file on your hard drive and double-click the file to start the installation.

You will be asked for a temporary folder to extract the files that are needed for installation. By default, this is a new folder on your desktop. You can enter any other drive and folder.

Next, the files will be extracted to the folder and the Setup.exe program inside that folder is started automatically. Double-click the file named Setup.exe if it does not start automatically.

- A guided installation dialog will begin and will step you through the installation process.

- If you want to install to another drive and folder than the default 'C:\Program files (x86)', choose the User Defined setup and change the path.

For AOO 4. x, the next folder will be created:

'C:\Program Files (x86)\OpenOffice 4'

- After installation is finished, you should not delete the folder with the extracted files, because these files will be required for repair via the Windows system manager.

- Start Apache OpenOffice with the desktop icon, or from the OpenOffice menu in your Start menu.

2. Install via Microsoft Store (Example for Windows 10 / 11)

Open the Microsoft Store App on your computer and search for "Apache OpenOffice". Alternatively, you can go to the [Web Store](#) and open the Store App from there.

- Click on the "Install" button.

- After downloading the installation file you will be asked for permission to install. After successful installation, the button changes to "Installed".

- Start Apache OpenOffice with the desktop icon, or from the OpenOffice menu in your Start menu.

3. Installing OpenOffice.org on Mac OS X

Find the icon with the download option on the top menu bar of the website by going to the OpenOffice website at <https://www.openoffice.org>.

When you click on it, a green area containing several choices will appear. Make sure OS X (version ≥ 10.7) (DMG) is chosen as your operating system (unless you have an earlier Mac, in which case 32-bit would apply).

Click on Download complete installation after choosing the version and language.

- Download the .dmg installation file.
- The AOO symbol should be dropped into the Application icon.

Category: Documentation/FAQ/Installation

9. Related Work

There have been many works about Apache OpenOffice, both about how it was made and how it is used as an office software package. Here are just a few:

The creation of Apache OpenOffice's source code is an example of a similar task. The source code is open for everyone to see, and coders can help improve it through the Apache OpenOffice project. There have also been studies about the community and development process behind Apache OpenOffice. For example, one study looked at how the program changed over a 10-year time (2001–2011). Adoption by users is another work tied to Apache OpenOffice. People and businesses use it. There have been studies on how Apache OpenOffice is adopted and used in different settings, like one that looked at how the software is used in the public sector in Spain. This study found that many government offices use Apache OpenOffice and that it saves money and makes it easier to work with other programs than proprietary software. Apache OpenOffice's ability to work with other apps and file types is a connected topic. Researchers have looked at how well Apache OpenOffice works with different operating systems and file formats. For example, one study looked at how well the software works with Microsoft Office file formats. This study found that Apache OpenOffice could open and change most Microsoft Office documents, which could help users who need to work with files from different sources.

Overall, there have been a number of works about Apache OpenOffice that have looked at how it was made, how many people use it, and how well it works with other programs and file types. These studies give users and creators

information about the pros and cons of the software, which can help them decide how to use it.

10. Conclusions

Apache OpenOffice is a free and open-source office suite that includes a word processor, spreadsheet program, presentation software, graphics editor, and database management system. It is available for multiple operating systems, including Windows, macOS, and Linux, and it supports many file formats, including those used by Microsoft Office.

In conclusion, Apache OpenOffice is a powerful and versatile office suite that offers many features and tools for creating and editing documents, spreadsheets, presentations, and graphics. It is a great alternative to expensive proprietary software and provides a cost-effective solution for individuals and organizations that need to create and manage office documents. However, it is worth noting that Apache OpenOffice has not received as many updates and improvements as some other office suites, and it may not be suitable for users who require the latest features and functionalities. Overall, Apache OpenOffice is a solid choice for users who need a reliable and free office suite.

- **AbZilla**, the Mozilla address-book project - <http://abzilla.mozdev.org>
- **SDBC**, OpenOffice.org's database access framework - <http://dba.openoffice.org/>
- **XPCOM**, Mozilla's object component technology - <http://www.mozilla.org/projects/xpcom>
- **UNO**, OpenOffice.org's object component technology - <http://udk.openoffice.org/>
- **MAPI**, Windows Messaging API - http://msdn.microsoft.com/library/?url=/library/en-us/mapi/html/_mapi1book_legal_information_2.asp?frame=true